

PENANAMAN INTERNAL BRANDING DALAM MEMBANGUN BRAND COMMITMENT

Nurul Azizah dan Siti Ning Farida

¹Program Studi Administrasi Bisnis, UPN “Veteran” Jawa Timur

¹Jalan Raya Rungkut Madya, Surabaya, 60293

e-mail: nurulazizah.adbis@upnjatim.ac.id

ABSTRAK

Memasuki revolusi industry 4.0 seluruh organisasi dituntut untuk meningkatkan daya saing di era global. Dalam berdaya saing suatu organisasi harus memiliki keunikan atau sering disebut dengan istilah *branding*. *Branding strategy* sering digunakan perusahaan swasta dalam membentuk loyalitas dan kepuasan pelanggan. Selain perusahaan swasta, di era global ini, perusahaan negeri –non-profit- juga dituntut demikian. Dalam membentuk atau memperkuat *branding* suatu organisasi diperlukan *brand commitment* yang baik agar tujuan organisasi tercapai. Dalam penelitian terdahulu diketahui bahwa *brand commitment* dipengaruhi oleh *brand orientation* dan *brand involvement* dari pelaku internal. Sehingga berkaitan dengan *career stage* pegawai di suatu organisasi. Kampus UPN “Veteran” Jawa Timur merupakan organisasi pendidikan negeri baru, yang memiliki *brand* sebagai kampus “Bela Negara”. Kemudian dalam penelitian ini dilakukan pada sampel sejumlah 285 di UPN “Veteran” Jawa Timur. Variabel yang digunakan terdiri dari *career stage*, *brand orientation*, *brand involvement* dan *brand commitment* dengan skala pengukuran yang diadaptasi dari penelitian terdahulu. Kemudian uji hipotesis dilakukan dengan uji ANOVA dan regresi linear. Kemudian diperoleh kesimpulan bahwa, terdapat perbedaan tingkat *brand orientation* berdasarkan *career stage*, sedangkan pada *brand involvement* dan *brand commitment* tidak terdapat perbedaan berdasarkan *career stage*. Kemudian hasil uji regresi linier menunjukkan bahwa terdapat pengaruh yang signifikan diantara variabel *brand orientation*, *brand involvement* dan *brand commitment*.

Kata Kunci: *Career Stage, Brand Orientation, Brand Involvement, Brand Commitment, Higher Education*

Fullpaper Download at <http://openjournal.id/sasanti/index.php/JDAM/index>

DAFTAR PUSTAKA

- Aaker, D. (1996). Measuring brand equity across products and markets. *California Management Review*, 38(3), 102–120. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41165845>
- Allen N J and Meyer J P. (1993a). Organizational Commitment: Evidence of Career Stage Effect. *Journal of Business Research*, 26, 49–61.
- Allen N J and Meyer J P. (1993b). The Measurement and Antecedents of Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63(1), 1–18.
- Bastos, W., & Levy, S. J. (2012). A history of the concept of branding: practice and theory. *Journal of Historical Research in Marketing*, 4(3), 347–368. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17557501211252934>
- Baumgarth, C. and Schmidt, M. (2010). How strong is the business-to-business brand in the workforce? An empirically-tested model of “internal brand equity” in a business-to-business setting. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 39(8), 1250–1260.

- Biedenbach, G., & Manzhynski, S. (2016). Internal branding and sustainability: investigating perceptions of employees. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(3), 296–306. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBM-06-2015-0913>
- Burmman, C., & Zeplin, S. (2005). Building brand commitment: A behavioural approach to internal brand management. *Journal of Brand Management*, 12(4), 279–300. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.bm.2540223>
- Burmman, C., Zeplin, S., & Riley, N. (2009). Key determinants of internal brand management success: An exploratory empirical analysis. *Journal of Brand Management*, 16(4), 264–284. <https://doi.org/10.1057/bm.2008.6>
- Dr. Timbul Siahaan. (2016). BELA NEGARA DAN KEBIJAKAN PERTAHANAN. In media informasi kementerian pertahanan (pp. 6–16).
- Du Preez, R., & Bendixen, M. T. (2015). The impact of internal brand management on employee job satisfaction, brand commitment and intention to stay. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 33(1), 78–91. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-02-2014-0031>.
- Ewing, M. T., & Napoli, J. (2005). Developing and validating a multidimensional nonprofit brand orientation scale. *Journal of Business Research*, 58(6), 841–85
- Grönroos, C. (1984). A service quality model and its marketing implications. *European Journal of Marketing*, 18(4), 36–44.
- Iglesias, O, Markovic, Stefan Rialp, Josep. 2018. How does sensory brand experience influence brand equity? Considering the roles of customer satisfaction, customer affective commitment, and employee empathy. *Journal of Business Research*. 0-1.
- Joung, H., Goh, B. K., Huffman, L., Yuan, J. J., & Surles, J. (2015). Investigating relationships between internal marketing practices and employee organizational commitment in the foodservice industry, 27(7), 1618–1640. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-05-2014-0269>
- Keller, K. . (2013). strategic brand management: building, measuring, and managing brand equity (4th ed.). boston: Pearson.
- Kotler, P., Jain, D.C. and Maesincee, S. (2002). *Marketing Moves: A New Approach to Profits, Growth, and Renewal*. Harvard Business School Publishing Corporation. boston.
- Levinson D J. (1986). A Conception of Adult Development. *American Psychologist*, 41(1), 3–13.
- Liu, G. C., Chris Ko, Wai Wai Ngugi, & Isaac K. 2015. The Role of Internal Branding in Nonprofit Brand Management: An Empirical Investigation. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 44 (2), 319-339
- Modi, A., & Patel, J. D. (2012). Employees' Brand Commitment and Career Stages: Empirical Evidence from Indian Universities. *THE IUP Journal of Brand Management*, IX(1), 28–40.
- Piehler, R., King, C., Burmann, C., & Xiong, L. (2016). The importance of employee brand understanding, brand identification, and brand commitment in realizing brand citizenship behaviour. *European Journal of Marketing*, 50(9/10), 1575–1601. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-11-2014-0725>
- Pinar, M., Trapp, P., Girard, T., & E. Boyt, T. (2014). University brand equity: an empirical investigation of its dimensions. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 28(6), 616–634. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-04-2013-0051>

- Powell, S. M. (2011). The nexus between ethical corporate marketing, ethical corporate identity and corporate social responsibility: an internal organisational perspective. *European Journal of Marketing*, 45(9/10), 1365–1379.
- Punjaisri, K., & Wilson, A. (2011). Internal branding process: Key mechanisms, outcomes and moderating factors. *European Journal of Marketing*, 45(10), 1521–1537
- Singh, A. K., & Singh, A. P. (2010). Career Stage and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour among Indian Managers. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 36(2), 268–275.
- Super D. (1957). *The Psychology of Careers*. new york.
- Super D E. (1984). *Career and Life Development*. san-fransisco: jossey-bass.
- Tseng, Ting hsiang Huang, Hazel H. Setiawan, Adilina. 2017. How do motivations for commitment in online brand communities evolve? The distinction between knowledge- and entertainment-seeking motivations. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 77 (1), 326-335.
- Varey, R. J. (1995). Internal marketing: a review and some interdisciplinary research challenges. *Internal Marketing: A Review and Some Interdisciplinary Research Challenges*, 6(1), 40–63.
- Wulandari, S. (2017). An Empirical Study on the Influence of Students ' Awareness on the Brand Identity : A Case of Telkom University Indonesia, 1(1), 54–59.